

**ABOUT ARABISMS SPECIFIC TO THE NAME AND ADJECTIVE
GROUP IN ALISHER NAVOYI TAZKIRAS**

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Annotation. Alisher Navoi has a special importance in Turkish literature with his prolific work. To date, the analysis of Arabisms in the linguistic study of Navoi's works has not yet been widely studied. Therefore, this article analyzes the Arabicisms related to the noun and adjective word group in the writer's essays "Nasoyimu-l-muhabbat" and "Majolisu-n-nafayis".

Key words: Arabicism, tazkira, nouns gender, number, agreement, case, morphology.

Introduction

In Arabic, nouns include nouns, adjectives, numerals, pronouns, adverbs, infinitives, and adjectives. Examples of these are the following words used in "Nasoyimu-l-muhabbat" and "Majolisu-n-nafayis": book, hazrat, ahl, waqf, naf', Arabic, khram, mutaammil, dakhil, jumla, olam, talent, nickname, Zoyl and others.

In Arabic, nouns have gender, number, agreement and case categories. In Alisher Navoi's tazkiras, phrases and sentences quoted from Arabic sources, as well as the names of persons and famous adjectives given to them, have preserved the Arabic form, for example:

"Shaykh-l-Mashayikh Sheikh Abu Saeed Kharroz, who is known as Qamaru-s-Sufiya, and Shaykh-l-Islam Muqarrabi Hazrat Khaja Abd-l-Lah Ansari, my tabaqat, graduates, Jami Awliya-l-Lohdin ".

This sentence contains 29 words, 24 of which are Arabic.

"This faqir I recited first, I learned it, this is the last matla'. At the same time, I was between the ages of three and four, the saints would invite me to study and express some admiration, and the masnavis of Hazrat Maulana Jalali-d-din Rumi (may God rest in peace) say that I am a "ramali musaddas" in the weight of the masnavis.

Data Collection

The above example contains 41 words, 21 of which are Arabic.

In these sentences, "Shayhu-l-Islam" is the sheikh of Islam, "Qamaru-s-Sufiya" is the "moon of Sufi (heaven)", "Abdu-l-Loh" is the servant of God, "Awliyau-l-Loh" is the guardian of God. , in Jalali-d-din phrases, the definite article is preserved in the compound isofa.

In other cases, Arabic words have been assimilated into the Turkish language and have adapted to the existing categories of the Turkish language. For example, there is no case category in Turkic languages, nouns in specific cases are not found in the work.

It is known that words that denote things such as a person, an animal, an item, or a thing are called nouns. As mentioned above, nouns in Arabic have gender, number, agreement and case categories. In Arabic, the gender of a noun does not change, it is either muzakkar or muannas gender¹. That is why, even though there is no gender category in Persian and Turkish languages, Arabic words have been assimilated in writing, keeping their muzakkar and muannas form, but it has no power as a grammatical category.

Analysis. Nouns are divided into common nouns or common nouns. There are two types of related nouns: nouns with a concrete meaning; nouns with abstract meanings. According to this classification, the following examples can be cited from

¹ Қ.: Гранде Б.М. Курс арабской грамматики в сравнительно-историческом освещении. – Москва: Восточной литература, 1963. – С. 116-120.

Alisher Navoi's poems:

- nouns with concrete meaning: creation, sky, surat, book, abbov, scientist, shuaro, master;

- nouns with an abstract meaning: intelligence, knowledge, blessing, service, hadith, sect, assembly, regret, thanks, address.

A proper noun is a noun that names a person, animal, or thing.

Many Arabic nouns are found in Tazkiras, such as people's names, nicknames, geographical names. For example:

Sheikh Faridi-d-din Attar, Sheikh al-Mashayikh Sheikh Abu Said Harroz, Sheikh Abu-l-Abbas Omili, Sheikh Ibrahim Ajari, Sheikh Abu-l-Hasan, Sheikh Banan; Egypt, Akhmim, Maghreb, Baghdad, Kirwan, Mecca, etc.

Unlike Turkic languages, Arabic has three grammatical numbers: singular, dual, and plural.

The Arabic binary muzakkar or muannas gender is a noun in the singular number that is removed from the end of the noun and replaced by ن - is made by adding the suffix. The dual word found in "Nasoyimu-l-muhabbat" is "madinataini" in the karatqich-tushum conjugation - the word for two cities.

There are two ways to form the plural of words in Arabic: the correct plural form and the broken plural form.

Result. When forming the correct plural, adding a plural suffix to the end of the noun does not change the singular form. Muzakkar is the plural of the word that refers to a person of gender and his profession "ونَ" possessive adjective (يَنَّ) and the plural of muannas gender to its end "اتٌ" is formed by adding the suffix, Here ة letter to ت changed. For example: أربعين (арбаъин), عارفين (орифин), درجات (даражот), تصنفات (маснифот), مصنفات (мусаннафот), استلاحات (истилоҳот).

It can be seen that the correct plural formation in Arabic is the same as in Turkic languages. Only Turkic languages do not have a gender category, by adding the suffix "-lar" to any singular noun, the plural form of this noun is formed, and the plural form of

most of the Arabic nouns found in Navoi's lexicon is formed by adding "-lar" to the singular noun, that is, through the Turkish suffix. For example: murids, mahrams, strangers, bankrupts, breaths, buildings, wives, cabbages.

Another type of plural in Arabic is the broken plural. When forming a broken plural in a noun, other new consonants and vowels are added to the root of the word, and its singular form changes to another form. Multiples of this type are grouped by weights. In Tazkiras, the following nouns are found in the broken plural: asrar, ashab, arvah, ashkol, arbob, avlod, ahval, abbov, alfoz, ulama, kulub, kutub, ulum, rusum, avliya, akobir, kibor, maqasid, salatin, faroyiz, dakoig.

From the above examples *أفعال فُعلاء فُعولٌ فِعَالٌ فَعَالِلٌ مَفَاعِلٌ* we see that the plural form is used more often in the weights.

Among the Arabic words that have entered the Turkish language, although adjectives have a significant place, there are not many such words in Navoi's tazkiras.

In Arabic, the adjective changes in gender depending on the gender of the noun. There are two types of adjectives: substantive and artificial. If original adjectives already exist, artificial adjectives are formed by adding an adjective suffix to the end of the noun. The following examples of basic adjectives can be given from works: nazir, weak, azim, farig', asil, fakir, gharib.

Examples of artificial adjectives are as follows: Sufi, Wafi, Persian, Arabic, Zahiri, optional, Sayid, Kirami, Ali, Piri, Kirmani, Yazdi, Khorasani, Problem.

In Arabic, the root adjective is formed in more than 20 cases from the first form of three-consonant intransitive verbs. There are three of them: 1) simple (head); 2) increase; 3) there are comparative levels.

In "Nasoyimu-l-muhabbat" the following simple basic qualities are found

:فَعِيلٌ - *назир, заиф, азим, гариб, шариф*;

فَاعِلٌ - *фориг, қодир, комил, зоҳир, содиқ*;

أَفْعَلٌ - *ашраф, акбар, ашадд, ақалл, ағлаз*.

أَفْعَلٌ (муан.) Adjectives in verb form are adjectives denoting color, hue,

property, and physical condition. In tazkiras, adjectives of this weight are found mainly in the form of names of people. For example: Adham, Ahmed.

Substantivization (turning into a noun) takes place in the course of the adjective possessive, participle, and other parts of the sentence. For example: Personal names such as Siddiq and Abbas were formed as a result of root adjectives, and proper nouns such as Ahmed, Adham were formed as a result of accretive adjectives becoming nouns.

Relative adjective in Arabic (التَّسْبِئَةُ) refers to relative signs such as whether someone belongs to a place (state, nation) or what something is made of. Suffixes forming relative adjectives are suffixes for muzakkar gender and muannas for gender. Only relative adjectives in muzakkar can be found in tazkiras. These are: Piri, Sufi, Persian, Arabic, Zahiri, Sayyid, Sanadi, Makhdumi, Islami, Muflisi, Kokii, Yakdi, Tabrizi, Nishapuri, Ghaznavi, Rumi, etc.

Thus, Alisher Navoi's tazkiras are rich in Arabisms, among which singular nouns are used a lot, and adjectives are rare.

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